

Machine-Learning-Based Detection and Forecasting of Volcanic Activities

Based on Seismic, Geodetic and Gas Data

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ABSTRACT

Today, more than 600 million people worldwide are at risk of a possible volcanic eruption in their vicinity [1]. For some years now, there has been an approach to predict possible eruptions at an early stage using Machine Learning models, to prevent eruptions in the best case or to prepare crisis management [2].

Basically, different types of volcanoes produce different data, which is recorded and used for model trainings. The different types are primarily divided into "mafic" and "intermediate" or "silicic" volcanoes [1].

Since there are not always historically accurate records of a volcano's unrest, the main attempt is to predict possible eruptions over a shorter time span using seismic, geodetic and gas-based changes. In a study using data from the 2006 eruption of Augustine Volcano in Alaska, conducted by Manley et al, a Random Forest model has already been successful [3].

KEYWORDS

Machine Learning, Random Forest, Detection, Prediction, Forecast, Volcano, Volcanic Activities, Eruptions, Volcanology

INTRODUCTION

Volcanoes are among the most dangerous regions people are living close to in the entire world. More than 600 million people live in those areas or at least close to active volcanoes and are at the mercy of the dangers posed by them [1]. Due to this risk of volcanic activities, forecasts of eruptions are one of the central goals volcanology is dealing with. The ancient city Pompeii was destroyed by a volcano, same happened to the Cretan civilization, which was destroyed by a tsunami caused by a volcanic eruption [4]. Although a lot of the very active volcanoes are monitored continuously, accurate predictions when volcanic activities will happen remain pretty elusive [4].

Several attempts to predict and forecast volcanic activities show that the eruption style as well as the magnitudes vary extremely from volcano to volcano, and even within one single eruption the values fluctuate drastically [5]. Over the last 4 to 5 years the

application of Data Science and Machine Learning techniques has become more and more interesting to deal with the obtained data derived from volcanic activities. So far, one of the focus points regarding the application of these new methods has been in the classification of volcanoes, eruptions and their seismic signals [2], [6].

Many studies which are researching in the field of volcano seismology focus on earthquakes, which often serve as early signals for possible future eruptions. Those records include the location of the earthquake origin, the measured magnitudes, the evaluated peak frequencies and a count of the daily number of events [7].

OVERVIEW

The overall aim of this paper is dealing with the question if it is possible to predict or forecast volcanic activities with the help of Machine Learning approaches based on data like seismic and geodetic records. Those approaches can be used to mitigate risks related to volcanic activities and would be useful for prevention, crisis management and recovery reasons [2]. For the forecast itself there will be a closer look at the Random Forest model.

1 VOLCANOES AND VOLCANIC ACTIVITIES

There is a broad variety of active volcanoes around the world, which mainly differ in morphology, evolution and the style of the eruptions. The various types of volcanoes produce different data, which gets monitored, stored and used for the model trainings. Those differences mainly depend on the tectonic settings, the magma as well as the eruption conditions which are representing the volcanoes. For a better overview, volcanoes can be divided into "mafic" and "intermediate" or "silicic/felsic" volcanoes [1].

1.1 Mafic Volcanoes

Mafic lava has a lower viscosity in comparison to the "felsic" lava due to the lower silica content in it. The word "Mafic" is a creation consisting of the terms MA (from magnesium) and FIC (Latin word for iron) [1]. Mafic volcanoes can appear in many different scales

and construction styles, one of the best-known forms of these kinds of volcanoes are the so-called shield volcanoes. A famous example is the Mauna Loa Volcano on the Hawaiian Islands, which you can see in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Picture of the Hawaiian Mauna Loa Volcano [1]

Remarkable are the relatively low slopes which emerge due to successive fluid lava flows. The Hawaiian shield volcanoes consist of several stacks of those thick lava flows – magma reaches the earth surface, turns into lava, slowly flows down the slopes while the crystallization process starts. Because of this cooling process, the lava thickens and increases in viscosity [1].

Another imposing formation of volcanoes is the ‘stratovolcano’, like the Italian Stromboli, which is the namesake for the Strombolian eruption style. Figure 2 shows the Stromboli volcano. This eruption style is typically characterized by frequently appearing, small explosions, which occur due to the rise and bursting of large gas bubbles [8]. Stromboli volcano is one of the ‘open-system volcanoes’, where gases inside the volcano can move through the system freely. Besides that, this volcano is also able to produce lava flows and so called ‘paroxysmal’ eruptions [9]. This complex variety in eruption styles is due to the structure of the magma storage and transport system as well as the resulting alternation between eruptive activities, which take place near-surface, but also in the depth of the volcano [1].

Figure 2: Picture of the Stromboli in Italy [1]

1.2 Intermediate and Silicic Volcanoes

Stratovolcanoes count as intermediate volcanoes as well, they are described as steep-sided cones consisting of stacked, cooled lava flows and pyroclastic deposits. The Etna in Italy or the Fuji in Japan are two very well-known intermediate stratovolcanoes, which are constructed from viscous magmas which erupted explosively [1].

Stratovolcanoes carry the risk of a sector collapse or a caldera formation. In general, a sector collapse is accompanied by explosive activities around the volcano [10]. Those explosions are particularly lethal, they occur due to dome collapses and magma intrusion. The collapse of a caldera is the result of the retreat of large amounts of magma [11].

The Taupo volcano in New Zealand is one of the examples what could be a result if a very large caldera-forming eruption happens. Such eruptions create inverse volcanoes or central collapse depressions which are surrounded by pyroclastic fans [12].

2 DATA

When it comes to the data which needs to be collected to actually create a forecast for volcanic activities, scientists follow two mainly different approaches. On the one hand, there are the long-term forecasts which are based on geological and historical data and records. On the other hand, there are short- and intermediate-term forecasts which are based on several patterns in the monitored data [13], [14].

2.1 Long-Term Forecasts

Dealing with historical and geological records and data enables scientists to evaluate the potential likelihood of a given volcano and its possible future eruptions [15]. This is the underlying basis for most volcanic hazard assessments and a major component of the classification process of volcanic risks. Generally, it is assumed that those evaluations should be valid over a long time period, future activities will probably follow similar patterns like they did in the past [14].

Long-term forecasts of volcanic activities which were based on historical, geological records have already shown remarkable results in the past. One of the most famous examples may be the Mount St. Helens. Dwight Raymond Crandell and Donal Ray Mullineaux wrote the following lines in 1978:

“In the future Mount St. Helens probably will erupt violently and intermittently just as it has in the recent geologic past, and these future eruptions will affect human life and health, property, agriculture, and general economic welfare over a broad area ... The volcano's behavior pattern suggests that the current quiet interval will not last as long as 1,000 years; instead, an eruption is more likely to occur within the next 100 years, and perhaps even before the end of this century.” [16]

Just two years later the Mount St. Helens erupted, and the whole eruption led to an unprecedented catastrophe.

In 2006, Marzocchi and Zaccarelli investigated global eruption catalogs and found that volcanoes with short interevent times are more likely to be time-predictable compared to volcanoes with longer interevent times, which seem to follow a more random distribution in relation to eruption timing and eruption size [17].

2.2 Short- and Intermediate-Term Forecasts

In contrast to the long-term forecasts, short- and intermediate-term forecasts try to recognize the signs which a volcano displays before the eruption begins. Since the beginning of the monitoring process of active volcanoes several decades ago, numerous manifestations of volcanic activities have been discovered. That includes seismicity, ground deformation, thermal emissions as well as gases. All of those indicators can be found during the different stages of preruptive unrest, as the magma from inside the volcano accumulates and is rising towards the earth surface, which is shown in Figure 3 [14].

Figure 3: A stratovolcano showing potential precursors to an eruption [14]

One of the first signs for a potential future eruption could be the higher CO₂ emissions due to its faster ascent compared to magma [18]. Other signs are the ‘Deep Long-Period Earthquakes’ and the

aseismic inflation, which are caused by magma migration and magma accumulation [19], [20]. Ice and glacier melting, thermal anomalies and changes in the water chemistry do also count as indicators for possible upcoming eruptions [21]. As soon as the magma rises and enters chambers which are only a few kilometers beneath the earth surface, the number of ‘Volcano-Tectonic Earthquakes’ is increasing, the ground might get deformed and sulfur gases get emitted [22], [23]. Some volcanoes which include a larger groundwater area might change the H₂S emissions to SO₂ emissions since the groundwater is displaced by the rising magma [24]. The last signs before the magma reaches the surface are for example more explosions due to higher concentration of gasses like SO₂ and halogens and changes in the seismic velocity [25], [26].

Figure 4: Timeline of the data period, April 2005 to May 2006 [3]

One possible study which tries to use Data Science and Machine Learning models to forecast volcanic activities has been conducted by Manley et al., using data from the 2006 eruption of Augustine Volcano in Alaska. This data is shown in Figure 4. The graphic shows the time period from April 2005 to May 2006, the dashed vertical lines denote the beginning as well as the end dates for the eruptive period of the Augustine Volcano [3]. The horizontal lines at the top represent the non-eruptive and the eruptive training periods for the Random Forest model. Bar (a) shows the classification of activity, described by Power et al., while bar (g) represents the Concern Color Code Status of Augustine Volcano throughout the data period [27]. The other bars (b, c, d, e, and f) clearly show a more frequent occurrence of certain events like explosions (stars in (b)), extremely high SO₂ emission rates and more seismic events during the eruptive period [3].

3 MODELS

3.1 Random Forest

The first step before training a Random Forest model is the Data Preprocessing. Manley et al. used a set of 40 different features in total, consisting of 34 seismic, 4 geodetic and 2 gas features. The whole feature set can be found in the appendix, Table 1 – Table 3. This feature set has been used to train and test a Random Forest model [3].

For this study the data has been separated into a ‘non-eruptive’ and an ‘eruptive’ class and a 5-fold cross validation has been applied. For the non-eruptive training data, a time range from April 30, 2005 until August 24, 2005 has been selected, while the eruptive training period was January 10, 2006 – April 12, 2006. Since the dataset shows some missing values, two different interpolation methods have been applied: The Gaussian Process Regression Interpolation (GPR), as well as the Carry Last Value Forward Interpolation (CLVF) [3]. The results of the Random Forest classification are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Results of the multi-class approach using Random Forest Classification [3]

The gray squares in the graphic above in rows (a) and (b) show the non-eruptive or eruptive model output while the blue line below shows the training periods for each class. The black line at the top represents the time period when the eruption was occurring according to the database. The multi-class model with the CLVF-interpolated features classifies days as eruptive later than the GPR-interpolated features. The overall model agreement for the CLVF

model is about 86%, the GPR model is about 82%. The model identifies the change-point from the non-eruptive state to eruptive state between mid-November and mid-December, which matches some previous conceptual models and records from this time [3].

3.2 Other Models and Algorithms

The Random Forest is not the only algorithm that has already been successfully tested to predict certain volcanic events. To automatically predict Strombolian activities at the Mount Erebus in Antarctica a CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) was trained using infrared images. Due to its remote location, such automatic methods are urgently necessary [28].

Another promising approach is the usage of the global volcano monitoring platform “MOUNTS” (Monitoring Unrest from Space), which uses multisensory satellite-based imagery, ground-based seismic data and a CNN to support predictions of volcanic activities. The efficiency has been proven on several eruptions like the Kilauea 2018, Anak Krakatau 2018 or Piton de la Fournaise 2018 – 2019 [29].

Vietnam uses a DNN (Deep Neural Network) for landslide susceptibility mapping of active volcanoes due to the hazard related to those landslides. The DNN approach showed a considerable better performance there compared to other ML methods as SVM (Support Vector Machine), MLP (Multilayer Perceptron) or Random Forest [30].

4 DISCUSSION

The multi-class forecasting method described in this paper definitely has potential utility in forecasting. In the opinion of some scientists, for example Poland and Anderson, those Machine Learning approaches are underutilized resources so far, which could be an effect of the limited amount of useful, available training data [14]. The decision which model should be applied in the process of forecasting such volcanic activities involves consideration of the monitoring infrastructure available at the volcanoes as well as the past volcanic activities there. Multi-class approaches using a Random Forest like in the study above could be useful at volcanoes which are not inactive [3]. The best case would be that those volcanoes should display consistent signals, like the Piton de la Fournaise volcano, which already is a candidate for this kind of studies [5], [29].

The interpolation method is also one part which needs to be considered when using Machine Learning as a forecasting tool. Based on the study of Colopy et al., the Gaussian Process Regression is a method which already is in use in the healthcare sector because it is able to forecast patient vital signs beyond certain model training periods [31]. That is the reason why Manley et al. recommend taking the GPR into the domain of volcanic activity forecasting as well [3].

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The study of Manley et al. perfectly shows that indeed it is possible to predict and forecast volcanic activities based on seismic,

geodetic and other data. Depending on the amount and the quality of data monitored at a volcano, changes in its state can be used by a Machine Learning model like the Random Forest to forecast unusual activities over short- and intermediate terms. For a long-term forecast, historical data can also lead to success, as Dwight Raymond Crandell and Donal Ray Mullineaux have proven [16]. Considerations of the interpolation method as well as the overall used models are necessary for the purposes of forecasting eruptions. In conclusion, using Machine Learning approaches can be a great support in the future [1], [3].

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APPENDIX

Table 1. List of seismic features used as input variables. Features with Δ indicate the variation from one day to the next [3].

1. Event rate (all types)
2. Δ Event rate (all types)
3. Mean of dominant frequencies
4. Variance of dominant frequencies
5. 90 th percentile of dominant frequencies
6. 10 th percentile of dominant frequencies
7. Minimum of dominant frequencies
8. Maximum of dominant frequencies
9. Median of dominant frequencies
10. Δ of dominant frequencies
11. Mean of band ratio
12. Variance of band ratio
13. 90 th percentile of band ratio
14. 10 th percentile of band ratio
15. Minimum of band ratio
16. Maximum of band ratio
17. Median of band ratio
18. Δ of band ratio
19. Mean of peak amplitudes
20. Variance of peak amplitudes
21. 90 th percentile of peak amplitudes
22. 10 th percentile of peak amplitudes
23. Minimum of peak amplitudes
24. Maximum of peak amplitudes
25. Median of peak amplitudes

26. Δ of peak amplitudes
27. Mean of waveform standard deviation
28. Variance of spectral width of the largest peak of each event.
29. 90 th percentile of spectral width of the largest peak of each event.
30. 10 th percentile of spectral width of the largest peak of each event.
31. Minimum of spectral width of the largest peak of each event.
32. Maximum of spectral width of the largest peak of each event.
33. Median of spectral width of the largest peak of each event.
34. Δ of spectral width of the largest peak of each event.

Table 2. List of GPS features used as input variables List of geodetic features used as input variables. Features with Δ indicate the variation from one day to the next [3].

1. Vertical position of AV01
2. Δ of vertical component of displacement at AV01
3. N-S component of the baseline vector for AV02-AC59 station pair.
4. Δ of the N-S component of the baseline vector for AV02-AC59 station pair.

Table 3. List of gas features used as input variables. Features with Δ indicate the variation from one day to the next [3].

1. Interpolated SO ₂ value
2. Δ of interpolated SO ₂ value